

DEVELOPMENT OF HIGH PERFORMANCE DISCONTINUOUS FIBRES – FIBRE SURFACE MODIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

In increasing the material throughput of aligned short fibre composites using HiPerDiF technology, the stability of the fibres in aqueous solution needs to increase. Subsequently, a range of surfactants, typically employed to disperse carbon-based materials, have been assessed to determine the most appropriate. Methods to assess the dispersive power of the surfactants have been trialed, based on success in other studies. Single fibre fragmentation tests were a necessity to determine any changes to the fibre and matrix interfacial adhesion and rheometry compliments the study to understand the potential mechanisms of the improved stability of short fibres in aqueous suspension.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced thermoset composites will be under threat unless their sustainability can be addressed. Thermoplastic matrices – by their inherent nature – can be reprocessed, but the recycling of fibres leads to difficulties.

The High Performance Discontinuous Fibre (HiPerDiF) technology, invented and developed at the University of Bristol, is an effective and sustainable high performance Aligned Discontinuous Fibre Reforced Composite (ADFRC) manufacturing process, with the potential for high production throughput [1].

ADFRCs have the potential to offer mechanical properties (i.e. stiffness, strength and failure strain) comparable with those of continuous fibre composites provided that the fibre aspect ratio is high enough to allow load transfer and attain fibre failure instead of pull-out (i.e. fibre/matrix interface failure) [2]. Moreover, ADFRCs produced using HiPerDiF have demonstrated the capabilities to overcome three of the key limitations of conventional continuous fibre composite materials:

- The lack of ductility, *i.e.* their elastic-brittle behaviour, by hybridising different types of fibres (*e.g.* glass, carbon) or exploiting pull-out mechanisms [3];
- The difficulties in producing defect-free components of complex shape with high-volume automated manufacturing processes;
- Implementing a sustainable material lifecycle, *e.g.* the integration of production and end-of-life recycled waste in a circular economy model [4].

A schematic of the HiPerDiF discontinuous fibre alignment machine is shown in Figure 1. The fibres are suspended in water, accelerated through a nozzle and directed to a gap between two parallel plates. The alignment mechanism relies on the momentum change of the fibres at the impact with the furthestmost plate. The fibres then drop under gravity on a stainless-steel conveyor mesh belt with the majority of the water is removed by vacuum. The aligned fibre preform is transported along the conveyor belt and dried with infrared radiation. The dry aligned fibres preform is coupled with a thermoset or thermoplastic matrix and partially impregnated through the application of heat and pressure. Different

types and lengths of fibres can be mixed in the water suspension, this allows highly intermingled hybrids composites to be obtained.

Figure 1. The HiPerDiF technology

To realise the capabilities of the ADFRCs *via* HiPerDiF methodology, further development is needed to assist with the scale-up of the technology. The current limitations are: (1) the maximum fibre volume fraction in the water medium prior to nozzle ejection and (3) the interfacial adhesion between the fibres which has the potential to be optimised to maximise mechanical performance of the resulting composite. These developments are required to be in keeping with the ethos of HiPerDiF being a water-based system.

The target of this work is to determine an ideal solution for increased throughput and methods to quantify the enhancements (i.e. dispersion). Furthermore, mechanical testing on the single fibre level to quantify any changes.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 MATERIALS

Granoc XN-90, a pitch-based fibre, was used throughout this study; the low strain to failure rate is ideal for single fibre fragmentation testing and, furthermore, the fibre is commonly used with the HiPerDiF program as a high modulus fibre. The polymer matrix used for the single fibre fragmentation test was Gurit Prime 27 with a slow hardener. The properties obtained from the respective manufacturer of both fibre and matrix can be found in Table 1 and Table 2., respectively. The polymer matrix was cured, as per the manufacturer's guidelines: 7 hours at 65 °C.

Table 1. Fibre properties

Fibre Property	High Modulus Carbon Fibre
Commercial Name	Granoc XN-90
Diameter (μm)	10
Density (g/cm^3)	2.21
Stiffness (GPa)	860
Strength (MPa)	3430
Failure Strain (%)	0.398

Table 2. Polymer matrix properties

Polymer Property	
Commercial Name	Prime 27
Cured Density (g/cm^3)	1.139
Stiffness (GPa)	3.47
Strength (MPa)	73.3
Failure Strain (%)	4.5

2.2 FIBRE CHARACTERISATION

2.2.1 ZETA POTENTIAL

The surface charge of the HMC fibres was determined using a streaming zeta potential (SurPASS 3 Electrokinetic Analyzer, Anton Paar). The zeta potential and the isoelectric point (IEP) were determined using a cylindrical cell of the instrument in the presence of a 1×10^{-3} M of KCl at various pH, adjusted with 0.05 M HCl or 0.05 M KOH. The cell was titrated in the direction of the IEP, then subsequently rinsed with 3 X 200 ml and 2 X 200 ml 1×10^{-3} M KCl. Thereafter, a pH scan to pH commenced.

The zeta potential, ζ , is calculated from the streaming potential measurements according to the following equation.:

$$\zeta = \frac{dU}{dp} \times \frac{\eta}{\varepsilon \varepsilon_0} \times \kappa_B \quad (1)$$

Where dU/dp is the streaming potential versus the differential potential pressure, η is the electrolyte viscosity, ε_0 is the permittivity and ε is the dielectric coefficient of the electrolyte and κ_B is the electrolyte conductivity

2.2.2 THERMAL STABILITY

The thermal stability of the fibres was assessed to determine the temperature to remove the polymer sizing whilst minimising damage to the fibres. The polymer sizing is typically a ~1 wt% epoxy resin applied to the fibre to aid handling and processing [5]. To aid reproducibility and clarity in the task of modifying and analysing the fibre surface, the sizing is removed. Furthermore, for the benefit of the HiPerDiF project, which would potentially couple thermoplastic/vitrimers.

To study the thermal stability, a simultaneous thermal analysis (STA) instrument (Netzsch STA 449 F1 Jupiter) was used, this allows for thermogravimetric (TGA) and difference scanning calorimetry (DSC) data to be obtained, however, in this work, only the TGA data were analysed. Approximately 10 mg of the fibres were added to Al₂O₃ crucibles and was subjected to a temperature increase from 30 °C to 600 °C at 10 K/min, under N₂ atmosphere.

2.3 DISSOLUTION

2.3.1 PRELIMINARY STUDY

A range of surfactants typically employed for carbon-based particulates in a liquid medium were initially assessed for their ability to aid stability of the short HMC fibres. These can be viewed in Table 3.

Table 3. List of surfactants used. List reproduced from: [6]

Surfactant	Chemical name	Composition	Molecular Weight	Surfactant Type
Brij 58	polyethylene glycol hexadecyl ether	C, H, O	1124	Non-ionic
Pluronic F127	poloxamer 407	C, H, O	12500	Non-ionic
SDS	sodium dodecyl sulfate	C, H, O, S, Na	288	Anionic
SDBS	sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate	C, H, O, S, Na	348	Anionic
Triton X-100	polyethylene glycol tert-octylphenyl ether	C, H, O	625	Non-ionic
Triton X-405	polyethylene glycol tert-octylphenyl ether	C, H, O	1968	Non-ionic
Tween 80	polyethylene glycol sorbitan monooleate	C, H, O	1310	Non-ionic

In the preliminary tests, 0.022 g, 0.22g and 2.2 g of each surfactant was added along with 22 mg of HMC and 20 ml of deionised water in a centrifuge tube. The solution was subsequently tip sonicated (Cole Palmer CPX750 (750 W max.) for 10 mins at 40% power, with pulse 5s on, 5s off and using 13 mm tip probe. For all samples, the tip was positioned at the same location with respect to the vessel/solution to minimise the dispersion variation from the processing technique. Following sonication, the solutions were agitated by hand for ~10 seconds and photographed at t = 0 and 5 mins. Lighting conditions were fixed and positions were kept as constant as possible, to minimise other variables.

Following the preliminary test, SDBS was prepared in concentrations of CMC (critical micelle concentration) = 100, 250, 500, 750, 1000 CMC in 30 ml solutions with deionised water. Foam was removed using isopropanol alcohol. ~33 mg of HMC fibres were added and the solution was tip sonicated for 3 mins, 2 seconds on, 5 seconds off at 20% power using a narrow tip. The solutions were mixed using a magnetic stirrer for 5 mins. Following mixing, the stirrer was switched off and photographs of the sample were taken at t = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mins. Solutions were agitated with a magnetic stirrer for ~20 seconds and added to a centrifuge tube and thus centrifuged for 30 mins and 7,500 g. The supernatant was removed and the dropped-out material was weighed after drying in the vacuum oven. This technique has successfully been employed using carbon nanotubes as opposed to short carbon fibres by King *et al.* [6]

2.5 RHEOLOGY

A TA Discovery HR-1 with a 40 mm/4° stainless steel cone-plate geometry (97 µm gap) and a Peltier plate. The viscosity was recorded as a function of shear rate between 1 and 150 s⁻¹.

2.6 SINGLE FIBRE FRAGMENTATION

Continuous HMC fibres were aligned in dogbone shaped-moulds and kept in tension using tape of both ends. For the surfactant-treated samples, the mould was used as a bath to submerge the fibres in the 1000 CMC solution. After 12 hours, the solution was removed and the fibres were left to dry for 1 hour. Prime 27 was prepared as per the manufacturers directions and carefully added to the moulds. The epoxy resin was cured at 65 °C for 7 hours.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of dogbone-shaped sample used for single fibre fragmentation tests

Samples were tested using a Shimadzu AGS-X tensile tester fitted with 10 kN load cell. Tests were conducted at a constant crosshead speed of 0.2 mm min⁻¹ and elongated by 2 mm [7], satisfying the criteria that the matrix is required to have a strain to failure three times greater than the fibre [7]. Samples were analysed using a Zeiss Imager M2 optical microscope.

The interfacial shear strength, τ , was calculated with the following equation:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f(l_c)d_f}{2l_c} \quad (2)$$

Where σ_f is the fibre strength at the critical length, d_f is the fibre diameter and l_c is the critical fragment length of the fibre ($l_c = 4l/3$) [8].

3. RESULTS

3.1 FIBRE CHARACTERISTICS

To determine the removal of the polymer sizing, TGA was conducted on the fibres that underwent the thermal treatment (Fig. 3). The results demonstrate successful removal, as typically, the response of a 'sized' fibre would be evident in a mass drop between 200 – 400 °C [9].

Figure 3. The thermogravimetric response of the HMC fibres.

The streaming zeta potential of the HMC, as seen in Fig. 4 reveals an IEP of ~2.8 pH and suggests stability from pH ~4 to 9.

Figure 4. The streaming zeta potential of HMC fibres.

3.2 PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENT

Through comparing a range of surfactants, typically used in dispersing carbon-based material, the best surfactant was determined to be SDBS; after 5 mins fibres were still suspended in the solution. However, this was only observed for the highest concentration tested. The only other surfactant which gave stable fibre suspension at $t = 5$ mins was Pluronic F127. Interestingly, in terms of the critical micelle concentration (CMC), Triton X-100, Brij 58 and Tween 80, are at a greater multiple of CMC, but this did not lead to improved fibre stability in solution. However, it is unknown as to how the CMC has shifted with the incorporation of the HMC fibres.

Figure 5. Dissolution experiment at $t = 0$ and $t = 5$ mins for different concentrations of SDBS (b-f), compared to the benchmark sample (a).

3.3 DISSOLUTION

The result of the preliminary test informed the main dissolution experiment, both for surfactant type and concentration. After a 5 minute agitation using a magnetic stirrer, the fibre solution was left in a steady state for an additional 5 minutes and was photographed every minute. The results can be seen

in Fig. 5 for $t = 0$ and $t = 5$ mins, for each surfactant concentration and a benchmark sample (no surfactant). Evidently, fibres have improved stability when the surfactant solution (with respect to CMC) is $750 + \text{CMC}$.

The solutions were agitated using magnetic stirring and were added to a centrifuge for 30 mins at 7500 G. These conditions have been reported to result in compressed, dropped-out material that could be weighed and thus used to determine dispersion power [6]. However, for short fibres the phase between dropped-out material and supernatant was not clear, making comparisons between each centrifuged sample difficult. Furthermore, it was noted for 1000 CMC that surfactant residue was visible in the dropped-out material, essentially hindering measurement.

The addition of surfactant would increase the viscosity which would assist with the stability of the fibres, increasing the fluid drag on the fibres. Subsequently, rheometry was conducted on the fibres and the results can be observed in Fig. 6. The aqueous solution demonstrates shear thinning behavior – in particular, for the solutions with the lowest SDBS concentration. Evidentially, when the concentration increases from 500 to 750 and 1000 CMC, the viscosity increases markedly. This coincides with the dispersion performance of these two high surfactant solutions (750 and 1000 CMC).

Figure 6. The rheological response of the aqueous-SDBS solution.

Increasing the viscosity of the solution can have a detrimental effect on the morphology of the fibres. Fig. 7 compares a benchmark ('Without PVA') and an identical sample containing polyvinyl alcohol (5 wt.%) ('With PVA') and it can be clearly be seen that the fibres have curled up. Furthermore, the fibres can lead to further flocculation. This effect was not seen for the SDBS modified samples.

Figure 7. Viscous of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) aqueous solution causing the fibres to curl up.

3.4 SINGLE FIBRE FRAGMENTATION

Given the potential modification to the surface of the HMC, performing mechanical characterisation to the fibre – matrix interface is crucial. The single fibre fragmentation was performed on unmodified, benchmark samples ($n = 5$) and surfactant-coated fibres (HMC). The fragmented lengths for each fibre type were measured to be within error for both BM and surfactant modified sample: $(433 \pm 42) \mu\text{m}$ for BM and $(438 \pm 6) \mu\text{m}$ for the SDBS modified sample – as can be seen in Fig.8. The interfacial shear strengths were therefore similar: for the BM sample - 29.7 MPa, compared to 29.3 MPa for the SDBS modified sample.

Figure 8. Average fragment length and the interfacial shear strength (IFSS)

5. CONCLUSIONS

Increasing the stability of the short fibre in water can be achieved with the use of surfactants, however, it is unknown as to the mechanism. Given the dimensions of the fibres, it is expected that gravity will dominate, thus increasing the viscosity is a fairly obvious method to stabilise the fibres in

solution. However, viscous fluids are capable to curl up the fibres, which would be detrimental to the HiPerDiF process of aligning fibres. Determining the dispersion power of surfactants by weighing dropped-out material was unsuccessful, thus, monitoring the settling of the fibres with time has proven to be the most effective way. As demonstrated by the single fibre fragmentation, the addition of the surfactant does not have an effect on the interfacial adhesion. It should be noted, that this is in comparison to a sized removed fibre. The addition of a polymer sizing is expected to increase the interfacial shear strength, thus reducing fragmentation length.

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